

VITULIA QUESTIONNAIRE

The following questions regard your food allergy.

You can ask your parents for help, but they can't tell you the answers.

Write "X" in the box of your chosen answer.

You can choose from these answers:

Very discomfort

Little discomfort

No discomfort

How much it bothers you...			
1. Have a food allergy			
2. Be always careful what you eat			
3. Eat only certain foods			
4. Don't eat the same things as your classmates/friends			
5. Not knowing the taste of some foods			
6. See classmates/friends eat all foods			
7. Feel bad if you ate foods you can't			
8. Don't try new foods			
9. Eat outside home (parties of friends, school trips...)			
10. Do not eat the food you are allergic to			

Emotions: 1,2,4,6,7
Restrictions: 3,5,8,9,10

How is your allergy since your last visit?

